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Research Article

**STUDY PERFORMED OBSERVATIONS ON THE FACTORS
WHICH CAN CAUSE THE DISEASE OF THE HYPERTENSION
IN THE ADULT PAKISTANIS****¹Aroosa Khalid, ²Sara Ansari, ³Javeria Tariq**
¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

There is so much diabetic disease reported in Pakistan, which is the cause of death. It also includes many other problems. These diseases of diabetes hypertension is very common in people nowadays so the purpose of this report is to show that the cases and the improvements which held in few years. It is also stated that in past few years the amount of diabetic patient increases rapidly throughout the Pakistan mostly in Lahore the report based on the hospital Mayo Hospital Lahore the most of the diabetic patients are at the age of 30 and above. Current cases reported at the Mayo hospital Lahore is 107 subjects of diabetic patients in which 26% is female and 74% is male. All the tests of the patient are held under the guidance of doctors and professional nurses of Mayo Hospital Lahore. The entire tests were held to analysis of diabetes and the hypertension among Pakistani adult. The main goal ad objective of Mayo Hospital Lahore is to find the cure and to help the patient who is suffering from diabetes and hypertension. It was very big and difficult challenge for Mayo Hospital Lahore but with the senior doctors and trained nurses the Hospital successfully completed this job.

Keyword: Hypertension, diabetes prevalence, Diabetes mellitus, smoking habit, less physical activities, percentage of patients suffering from diabetes, BMI, Health.

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INTRODUCTION:

The disease of diabetes and hypertension is very dangerous because it can lead to death of the patient. It can also harm many of the other parts of the body, which can be very painful and difficult to handle in the same time [1]. There are some symptoms of hypertension in the diabetes that are restlessness, laziness, difficulty in breathing, weight loss, pale skin, heart disease, Kidney pain, and many more. However, the diabetic patients cannot take Spain bye underlying renal disease and remains important [2, 3, 4]. The data which doctors of Mayo Hospital Lahore have collected from many patient they come to know that Type 2 of diabetes played important role in hypertension and the prevention of hypertension. In Pakistani adult according to the research, it is also reported that 63 million adults who are at their 32 To 40 years old are mostly suffering from diabetes and hypertension [5, 6]. In one of the studies the doctors come to know that 64% of the majority of the Pakistani adults who live in rural areas are suffering from diabetes. According to these reports which are collected by Mayo hospital Lahore the doctors come to know that diabetes play an important role in medical history and increasing day by day [7, 8, 9, 10]. It is also important to study the cause of diabetes and hypertension in Pakistani adult. According to some theories the doctors come to know that socioeconomic variable is the cause of diabetic hypertension among Pakistani adult smoking habit and Restaurant foods also enhancing the risk of diabetes in adult of Pakistan

METHODOLOGY:

For the purpose completion of this report the doctors study the reports of hundred patients who is suffering from diabetes and they find out that in Pakistan there are 70% diabetic adults. This data was collected by some of the doctors and trained nurses from the Mayo hospital Lahore to see the cause of this and also how diabetes hypertension among Pakistani adult are increasing. To complete this report the doctors and nurses divide this report according to

their ages and other socioeconomic variables of the family like how many members are suffering from diabetes in whole family, the personal information were also collected about the age married status height BP and the patient who is suffering from diabetes and rules BMI is less than 20 is also considering in this group. According to the analysis the doctors and the nurse they come to know that the percentage of male diabetic patient is more than the female diabetic patients and also the percentage of diabetic patients from rural areas are higher than urban areas as it is shown in the table of valence of diabetic hypertension that there is a major difference between the percentage of ruler patients and the urban patients. of majority of the diabetic patients who is suffering from hypertension is above then age of more than 40. The data of the diabetic patients are collected according to age of diabetic patient personal data of diabetic patient and for how long the patient is suffering from diabetes yes we all can see the prevalence of diabetic hypertension is increasing Pakistani adult but not all of the adult patients is subset from similar period. Some of the patients are suffering more than 10 year of their diabetes and some of them are even less than 2 years

RESULT:

According to the analysis and observation there is an increase rate of diabetes and hypertension in the adults of Pakistan if the rate of diabetes increases like this day by day then it can be very dangerous for the adults and also for the older people because it can lead to death and also can be inherited by the other family member which is not a good sign so it is important to control and take precautionary measurements according to the reports and observation the habit of restaurant food and less physical activities can lead to 2 diabetes and hypertension there are three important variables that play important role in the prevalence of diabetes and hypertension that are age marital affairs and food, Diabetes is dangerous disease that can cause death if the sugar level become so much high.

Table 2: Results of factor analysis for both groups of adults.

Socioeconomic variable	Prevalence of diabetes hypertension				Non-prevalence of diabetes hypertension		
	Communality 1st	Communality, 3rd	Coefficient-1	Coefficient -2	Communality, 1st	Communality, 4th	Coefficient
Residence	0.133				0.086		
Religion	0.089				0.125		
Gender	0.743	0.843	-0.633	0.658	0.84		
Marital status	0.228				0.531	0.621	-0.788
Age	0.048				0.493	0.605	0.778
Education	0.386	0.342	0.529	-0.248	0.441		
Occupation	0.398	0.451	-0.258	0.608	0.549		
Income	0.764	0.965	0.653	0.734	0.899		
Expenditure	0.788	0.966	0.682	0.707	0.899		
Utilization of time	0.083				0.758	0.78	0.883
Restaurant food	0.169				0.104		
Can food	0.561	0.665	-0.75	0.32	0.772		
Physical work	0.283				0.431		
BMI	0.21				0.07		
Duration of disease	0.214				0.266		
Smoking	0.329				0.258		

40 - 50	33	12.5	231	87.5	264	27.5
50+	69	27	187	73	256	26.7
Education						
Illiterate	11	20.4	43	79.6	54	5.6
Primary	22	19.1	93	80.9	115	12
Secondary	23	10	206	90	229	23.9
Higher	89	15.8	473	84.2	562	58.5
Occupation						
Agriculture and unskilled labor	34	13.3	221	86.7	255	26.6
Business and skilled labor	22	13.7	139	86.3	161	16.8
Service	27	12.7	186	87.3	213	22.2
Housewives and others	62	18.7	269	81.3	331	34.5
Income (in 000 taka)						
<40	51	16.4	260	83.6	311	32.4
40-60	30	15.9	159	84.1	189	19.7
60-80	29	15.7	159	84.3	188	19.6
80-100	18	11.3	142	88.7	160	16.7
100+	17	15.2	95	84.8	112	11.7

Use of can food						
Yes	106	18.2	478	81.8	584	55.2
No	39	10.4	337	89.6	376	44.8
Obesity						
Underweight	8	9.4	77	90.6	85	8.9
Normal	62	13.6	394	86.4	456	47.5
Overweight	51	15.6	276	84.4	327	34.1
Obese	24	26.1	68	73.9	92	9.6
Utilization of time						
Academic activities	4	2.9	135	97.1	139	14.5
Reading and watching T.V.	27	11.2	214	88.8	241	25.1
Games and sports	29	11.7	218	88.3	247	25.7
Paper reading and use of mobile	50	20.1	199	79.9	249	25.9
Use of T.V. and mobile	35	41.7	49	58.3	84	8.8
Physical exercise						
No	103	16.9	506	83.1	609	63.4
Yes	42	12	309	88	351	36.6
Total	145	15.1	815	84.9	960	100

DISCUSSION:

The result in this report is based upon the data collection and analysis of patients from the Mayo hospital Lahore. This data is recorded under some good doctors and trained nurses there is a high risk of disease among the adults of Pakistan. In the past few years the rate of diabetic patients and hypertension increase [10, 11, 12] it is because taking the bad quality food soft rings and also the things which we use in can and also less physical activities [13, 14, 15]. There are also some signs and symptoms that indicates the disease of of diabetes and hypertension that may include frequent urination feeling thirsty, hungry, always feeling tired, not a clear vision, if the patient have wound or cut the slow process of healing pain in hands and feet and also the dark skin. If any of these symptoms found in any patient then that patient may be suffering from diabetes type 2 with the passage of time the disease of diabetes and prevalence of hypertension becoming common according to the reports and other general researches held by Mayo hospital Lahore.

CONCLUSION:

According to the reports and records of patients the doctors and nurses of Mayo hospital Lahore come to the conclusion that day by day and the disease of diabetes and prevalence of diabetes and hypertension among Pakistani adult is increasing and the cause of this disease is vary from age to age and also the cause of prevalence of diabetes and hypertension among Pakistani adults are the in taking of food from different restaurants and can food because there is a high rate of bacteria that is present in the material of can in the other very important component of this disease is family inheritance because 40% of the patients which we have studied and the results come to know that they are suffering from diabetes because they have inherited this disease. After seeing these reports the doctor come to know that if the patients want to want to be healthy and recover from this disease they should follow some of the precautions that are to exercise daily, avoid restaurant and cane food, start eating healthy foods, exercise daily, quit

smoking and drinking take participate in physical exercise and activities take care of their weight and also check their BP and sugar daily and also to take medicines which is prescriptive by doctor after following all of these precautions the patient can survive and can avoid prevalence of diabetes and hypertension.

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